

“OCCASIONAL TRANSFORMATION IN PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES”

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses about the occasional transformation in phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages. It includes annotation, keywords, introduction, main part, conclusion and references.

Keywords: transformations, phraseological units, semantics, comparison of languages, phytonyms, expressions, phrases

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье речь идет об окказиональных трансформациях во фразеологических единицах английского и узбекского языков. Он включает аннотацию, ключевые слова, введение, основную часть, заключение и список литературы.

Ключевые слова: трансформации, фразеологизмы, семантика, сопоставление языков, фитонимы, выражения, словосочетания.

Phraseology has always made a huge contribution to the formation of a figurative picture of the world of all languages. it an integral part of the transmission of the cultural heritage of the people, with studying which you can get acquainted and study traditions, customs, values, life of this or that nation. Features of a particular language characterize phraseological units, have different expressive color, capable of acquiring additional meaning when they are influenced by context. Also they can refer to different functional styles. Studying the common features and differences of phraseological units of different languages, a better understanding of national identity can be achieved native speaker, to deepen knowledge of the language, because phraseological units are its bright component.

The main obstacle in the process of intercultural communication consists in the nationally specific characteristics of cultures, in contact with each other . Methods and Materials Studying nominations of a human with a phytonym component we used descriptive and analytical, comparative, linguistic and cultural methods. The method of continuous sampling from explanatory and phraseological dictionaries of the

English language: Oxford Dictionary of Idioms and Cambridge International Dictionary of Idioms and Anglo-Russian phraseological dictionary by A.V. Kunin.

In Uzbek, with the help of the following dictionaries:

O‘zbek tilining izohli frazeologik lug‘ati and O‘zbek xalq maqollarining izohli lug‘ati [Explanatory phraseological dictionary of Uzbek language and explanatory dictionary of Uzbek folk proverbs.

Let’s take definition of phraseological units from the linguistic dictionary, phraseological unit is the name of generalized by semantics phrases and sentences implemented in speech as fixed, stable turns of the semantic and a certain lexical and grammatical structure of the language. Today, there are many aspects and opinions in the study of phraseological units, both among supporters modern research methods, and among followers of traditional directions. Famous linguist V.N.Telia claims that for phraseological units full or partial non-deducibility of semantics is characteristic phraseological unit from a complex of meanings of components, that is idiomacy.

Phraseological units with a floristic component reflect human observations of the flora world for many centuries, convey the attitude of people to the nature around them and become the cultural foundation of the language. Phraseological units with a floristic component belong to a specific thematic group "phytonym", and reflect a certain sphere of the material world. They are relatively stable in semantic terms, their meaning does not change within the boundaries of special use. Over 70 units were identified with a floristic component, 17 of them with a “rose” component (for example, a rose without a thorn - “rose without thorns”, English rose - "English rose", a real English lady, bed of roses - "easy, happy life"), 11 of them with the “apple” component (for example, an apple of another tree is a completely different matter, apple-pie order is a sample, a perfect order, the apple of one’s eye is the apple of an eye), 8 with a “nut” component (a hard (tough) nut - "tough nut", the nuts and bolts - the basis of the foundations), 5 with the component "tree" (family tree - a family tree, flourish like a bay tree - to flourish, shake the pagoda- tree - get rich quickly), as well as 31 units with various other components (Be full of beans - to be full of energy, Couch potato - a slacker, a slothful person, (As) cool as a cucumber - a very reserved person, etc.) . Overall, the most frequently occurring phraseological terms are floronyms with the “rose” component, followed by floronyms with the “apple” component, then - with the “nut” and “tree” components.

The rarest floronyms with the components “bean”, “potato”, “cucumber”, etc. In Uzbek language we have analysed 75 phraseological units with phytonym, 15 with the component “flower” as “Gul tikansiz bo‘lmas”, 10 of them with “tree” component such as “Daraxt bir joyda ko‘karadi”, and 8 of them with the component “apple” e.g. “Olmaning tagiga olma tushadi” , 42 phraseological units with other c

omponents”wheat”(Bug‘doy o‘rilgach,o‘roqni zang bosadi) “barley”(arpa ekkan arpa olar),fruits and vegetables. By analyzing the dictionary definitions, we have established the meanings of phraseological units of the studied group. The subject of consideration was the lexical and semantic features, the metaphorical nature of phraseological units with a floristic component, the functional use of these units as a means of characterizing a person, as well as possible options for their translation into Uzbek.

The vast majority of the surveyed units characterize one or another side of a person’s life, his appearance, character or quality

A rose without a thorn- "an exceptional phenomenon" from the poem "The Girl from Richmond Hill" ("The Lass of Richmond Hill") by the Irish poet and playwright L. MacNelly (1752-1820): That girl was an exceptional case. Clever, kind and beautiful - a rose without a thorn. - It was an extraordinary girl. Smart, kind and beautiful is perfection itself. This phraseological unit describes the qualities of a person.

A young woman is usually compared to a rose. English rose- "An English girl with a fair complexion and regarded as classically beautiful" - "English rose", a real English lady; The Uzbek context denotes concept beauty by a flower, such as “gul tikonsiz bo‘lmas”. It should be mentioned, word “flower” implies beauty of a woman, besides “flower” signifies a young single girl in Uzbek context, as” Har gulning hidi boshqa”or “Gul o‘ssa yerning –ko‘rki, qiz o‘ssa elning- ko‘rki”.

A rose between two thorns - a (beautiful) woman among men is also applicable when describing a person. The phraseological unit as fresh as a rose - "blooming, looking beautiful" - is often used as a compliment and is most often applied to girls. Also, health (healthy complexion) is also associated with a rose: have roses in one’s cheeks - to have a blush on the whole cheek. In Uzbek face appearance described by fruit” yuzlari qirmizi olmaday” for making impressive description. They also describe the qualities of a person and phraseological units with other components.

For example, a hard (tough) nut - "a person or thing that is difficult to deal with, understand, or influence" - "tough nut to crack." In Uzbek context “nut” won’t imply human character but in metaphoric usage denotes “cheating” as “Qo‘ynini puch yong‘oqqa tuldirmoq”, Apple polisher- “someone who is always trying to impress or be nice to important or powerful people in order to gain an advantage” - “sneaky”. A rotten apple- “used about someone who is dishonest or immoral and who has bad effect on others” - “immoral person”.

The same analogue you may find in Uzbek context as” Bitta chirigan olma bir ombor olmani chiritadi”. Not amount to a hill of beans (not amount to a row of beans BrE) - to be worth very little or be of very little importance. - “mean nothing, cost nothing”. Be full of beans - to feel eager to do things and have a lot of energy- “lively,

energetic”. Somebody knows how many beans make five (British English) - used to say someone is sensible, especially about money.”

On his own mind, knows what is how much, knows what is what”. Mostly Uzbek people use phraseological units with agricultural crops as wheat, barley, rice, millet. Due to reason, they were not nomadic people and do farming in Central Asia region.

Couch potato- someone who spends a lot of time sitting and doing things that do not use much mental or physical energy, such as watching television. Instead of potato, in Uzbek melon denotes silly person as “Qovun qovundan rang oladi”.

As) cool as a cucumber- used about someone who stays very calm in a situation where you expect them to be nervous, upset, or embarrassed. - “very restrained person”. The grass roots- an ordinary people in an organization, rather than the leaders (often used in politics) - “from the bottom”. Thus, all of the above phraseological units in one way or another describe a person (appearance, character, any qualities).

To conclude with, sources of national-specific features of phraseological units with names of animals can serve as differences of species, their lifestyles, working conditions, value system, historical conditions of language formation of a certain ethnic group, etc [6]. National specific of phraseological units with names of phytonym is evident in different priorities of human activity, properties, nature, preferred, or condemn the personal qualities of men and women in different linguistic cultures, as well as that same phraseological unit, speaking different languages, can be attributed to various human qualities, or different animals may be "holders" of the same quality. Thus, the features of phytonymic phraseological units highlighted by us are not a complete reflection of the linguistic picture of the world, however, examining the national-cultural features of phraseological units, it can be argued that phytonyms convey their characteristics in phraseological units, such as the character of a human qualities and appearance. Also, phytonyms can denote actions of various kinds, financial and emotional state, mental health problems, hierarchical relationships.

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